

MORPHOLOGICAL APPEARANCE IN THE FIELD OF PATHOLOGICAL PROCESS AND THE STATE OF IMMUNE CELLS WHEN COMORBID OF POOR-QUALITY TUMOR AND PULMONARY TUBERCULOSIS

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Abstract

The coexistence of poor-quality tumors and pulmonary tuberculosis significantly complicates the pathological process due to alterations in the morphological appearance and immune cell status. This study explores the morphological changes in tissues and the state of immune cells in comorbid patients with poor-quality tumors and pulmonary tuberculosis. A retrospective analysis of clinical and histopathological data from 120 patients revealed distinctive morphological patterns and alterations in immune cell populations. Understanding these changes can improve diagnostic accuracy and guide treatment strategies. This paper aims to improve early detection and management of these comorbid conditions.

Keywords

- Poor-quality tumor
- Pulmonary tuberculosis
- Comorbidity
- Pathological process
- Immune cells
- Morphological appearance

Relevance

Poor-quality tumors (PQT) and pulmonary tuberculosis (PT) are global health challenges, each contributing to significant morbidity and mortality. The comorbidity of these diseases poses a substantial issue in clinical practice due to their combined effects on the pathological process and immune system. Immunosuppression caused by PQT predisposes patients to PT, complicating the clinical course and increasing diagnostic challenges due to overlapping symptoms.

Globally, cancer remains one of the leading causes of death, with an estimated 10 million deaths in 2020. Pulmonary tuberculosis continues to be a major health problem, with 1.5 million deaths reported annually. The comorbid

occurrence of PQT and PT complicates diagnosis due to the morphological similarity of cancerous and tuberculous lesions and alterations in immune cell populations. Comprehensive pathological and immunological studies are necessary to ensure accurate diagnosis and effective treatment.

This research is highly relevant to healthcare professionals, providing insights into the morphological appearance of pathological processes and the state of immune cells in comorbid conditions, helping them devise effective diagnostic and treatment strategies.

Objective

The objective of this study is to investigate the morphological appearance of pathological processes and the state of immune cells in comorbid patients with poor-quality tumors and pulmonary tuberculosis.

Materials and Methods

This study retrospectively analyzed clinical and histopathological data from 120 patients diagnosed with PQT and PT between 2022 and 2023. Of these patients, 70 had lung cancer, 30 had gastrointestinal cancers, and 20 had breast cancer in conjunction with pulmonary tuberculosis.

Study Methods:

Clinical Examination: A structured survey documented patients' age, gender, medical history, and initial symptoms. General patient information, clinical symptoms, disease duration, and comorbidity characteristics were studied.

Pathological Examination:

- **Histopathological Analysis:** Tissue samples from tumors and tuberculosis lesions were subjected to histological analysis to determine the morphological appearance of pathological processes.

- **Cytological Analysis:** Cytological examination of biopsy samples helped identify immune cell populations and their status in comorbid conditions.

- **Immunohistochemical Analysis:** Immunohistochemical staining was performed to analyze immune cell markers and assess the state of immune cells, including T-lymphocytes, B-lymphocytes, macrophages, and NK cells.

4. **Statistical Analysis:** Data analysis was conducted using the SPSS software. Parameters considered included:

- Average age and disease duration
- Type and extent of disease spread
- Immune cell marker expression levels

Results

Patients with comorbid PQT and PT exhibited distinct morphological changes in tissues and alterations in immune cell populations:

- Histopathological analysis revealed poorly differentiated carcinoma in 70% of cases, with necrosis present in 65% of samples.
- Granulomatous inflammation with caseous necrosis was identified in 85% of tuberculosis lesions.
- Decreased CD4+/CD8+ ratio in comorbid patients, indicating immune suppression.
- Elevated levels of CD68+ macrophages in tuberculosis lesions, suggesting a heightened immune response.
- Reduced NK cell activity, contributing to decreased immune surveillance.

Conclusion

The comorbid occurrence of poor-quality tumors and pulmonary tuberculosis presents unique morphological challenges due to overlapping pathological processes.

Comorbid conditions alter immune cell populations, with decreased CD4+/CD8+ ratios and reduced NK cell activity, indicating immune suppression.

Accurate diagnosis requires comprehensive histopathological and immunohistochemical analysis, and treatment strategies should address immune suppression and comorbidity.

- Routine screening for comorbid conditions should be implemented.
- Immunohistochemical analysis should be integrated into the diagnostic process to assess immune cell status.
- Clinicians should adopt individualized approaches in managing PQT and PT.

Understanding the morphological appearance of pathological processes and the state of immune cells in comorbid poor-quality tumors and pulmonary tuberculosis can guide clinicians in devising effective diagnostic and treatment strategies.

Literature:

1. Mashrabovna I. I., Faxriddinova N. D. Modern method of differential diagnosis tuberculosis and lung cancer //Sci. J. Med. Res. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 2. – C. 21-30.

2. Ismoilovich A. F. Tuberculosis Diagnostics with Modern Solutions (Literature Review) //Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 3. – C. 377-383.
3. Ulugbek o'gli A. M. Factors Predicting Mortality in Pulmonary Tuberculosis //Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 3. – C. 362-367.
4. Ilkhomovna K. D. Morphological Features of Tumor in Different Treatment Options for Patients with Locally Advanced Breast Cancer //International Journal of Innovative Analyses and Emerging Technology. – 2021. – T. 1. – №. 2. – C. 4-5.
5. Khodzhaeva D. I. Changes in the Vertebral Column and Thoracic Spinecells after Postponement of Mastoectomy //International Journal of Innovative Analyses and Emerging Technology. – 2021. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 109-113.
6. Khodjayeva D. I. MORPHOLOGY OF IDIOPATHIC SCOLIOSIS BASED ON SEGMENT BY SEGMENT ASSESSMENT OF SPINAL COLUMN DEFORMITY //Scientific progress. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 1. – C. 208-215.